

ECONOMIC ANALYSIS OF PROCESSING OF RICE BRAN OIL

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Abstract

The study was conducted on "Economic analysis of processing of rice bran oil" with the following objectives, viz. to workout the establishment cost of rice bran oil unit, to study the economics of processing of rice, to analyse the break even point of rice bran oil unit. The present study was carried out in Gondia district. The single rice bran oil unit was selected for the study. Economics of processing of rice bran oil unit calculated on the basis of primary data collected from the selected rice bran oil unit and result shows that the average capacity utilization of rice bran oil unit was 76.02%. The average capital investment for rice bran oil unit was Rs.1355.58 lakhs. The average annual fixed cost of rice bran oil was Rs. 855.36 lakhs. The average variable cost of the unit was Rs. 183.47 lakhs. The total marketing cost of rice bran oil unit was Rs. 90.31 lakhs. Gross returns of rice bran oil unit per ton was Rs. 71389.86 Net returns per ton of rice bran oil unit was Rs. 43883.49 The break even point of rice bran oil unit in physical terms was 1278.17 tons of oil, in monetary terms, it was analysed Rs. 91248323.29 The percentage of margin of safety was 31.14 per cent.

Key words: Paddy/ Rice, costs, economics of processing, break-even point.

Introduction

Processing of agricultural product has assumed great importance now-a-days. Processing creates form utility in the agricultural products which help in fetching high prices. Some of the agricultural products need processing so as to convert them in edible form viz., Paddy, sugarcane, pulses and oilseed needs processing to make them suitable for final consumption.

Rice bran is used for the enrichment of foods, due to its high dietary fibre content. Since the middle of the 1970s, the role of dietary fibre in health and nutrition has stimulated a wide range of research activities which caught public attention. In view of the therapeutic potential of dietary fibre, more fibre incorporated food products are being developed. Addition of dietary fibre to a wide range of products will contribute to the development of value-added foods or functional foods that currently are in high demand (Hu et al., 2009)

India is the world's second largest producer of rice and the largest exporter of rice in world. India's total rice production during 2022-23 crop year is estimated at a record 130.29 million tons as against 18.53 million tons in the previous year. Production increased from 53.6 million tons in 1980 to 120 million tons in 2022-2023. (www.statista.com)

In India paddy occupies the first place both in area and production. Apart from rice milling, processing of rice bran for oil extraction is also an important agro processing activity for value addition, income and employment generation

Maharashtra is a highly industrialized state of India, agriculture continues to be the main occupation of the state. In Maharashtra rice is the second important crop of the people, which is grown over an area of 14.99 lakh hectares with an annual rough rice production of 32.37 lakh tons. The average productivity of the state is 2.01t/ha. Maharashtra rank 13th place in rice production in country. (M.S. Research gate)

Table 1 : Capital utilization of Rice Bran Oil unit

Sr. No.	Particulars	Value in ton
1	Capacity of production per month in ton	540
2	Actual production in year 2022-23	4105 (76.02)
3	Capacity of unit per year	5400 (100.00)

It is revealed from Table 1. that, the selected unit of Rice Bran oil produces 540 tons of oil per month. Thus, the total capacity of production of unit per year was 5400 tons out of which 4105 tons produced in year 2022-2023.

Thus, it was concluded that capacity utilization of selected unit was 76.02 per cent.

Materials And Methods

The study was conducted in Gondia district at Shah Solvex Plant, Rice bran oil unit Adashi Ta. Dis. Gondia. The data was collected for FY 2022-2023 i.e. from March 2022 to April 2023 from the rice bran oil unit. This unit remains closed for two months in a year due to off season. Data were collected through personal interview method. The fixed cost, variable cost and total cost were calculated. Primary data are collected from rice bran oil unit (Processor). Keeping in view objectives of the study, appropriate statistical methods were used to analyse the data.

Break Even Point

The point at which the two curves i.e. total cost curve and total revenue (revenue means the total annual income) curve intersect is called the Break Even Point (BEP), which indicates level of production at which the producer neither losses money nor makes a profit.

Computation in physical quantity,

$$\text{Break even point} = \frac{F}{P-V}$$

Computation in monetary value,

$$\text{Break even point} = \frac{F}{(1-V/P)}$$

Where,

F = Total annual fixed cost in Rs.

P = Selling price per unit in Rs.

V = Variable cost per unit in Rs.

Results And Discussion**Capital utilization of Rice Bran Oil unit**

The capital utilization of rice bran oil processing unit is presented in Table 1.

Capital investment of rice bran oil unit

Capital investment was the acquisition of physical assets by a company or a unit for use in furthering its long term business goals and objectives.

Table 2 : Capital investment of rice bran oil unit

Sr. No.	Particulars	Rs/year (In lakhs)
1	Machinery	1310.60 (96.68)
2	Building and other structure	15.00 (1.11)
3	Investment on land	25.00 (1.84)
4	Furniture	2.98 (0.22)
5	Electricity installation charges	2.00 (0.15)
	Total	1355.58 (100.00)

It is revealed from the Table 2. that, the total capital investment in capital asset in Rice bran oil unit was Rs.1355.58 lakhs. The investment on machinery was the major investment accounted 96.68 per cent of the total investment followed by investment on land accounted 1.84 per cent of the total investment. The investment on building and other structure ranked as third important item of capital investment was 1.11 per cent. The investments on office furniture and

electricity installation charges were stood as negligible items on investments accounting for 0.22 per cent and 0.15 per cent respectively of total investment cost.

Annual fixed cost of Rice bran oil unit

The fixed cost includes the data regarding the cost of machinery, building, furniture, employee's salary, taxes, insurance and interest on fixed capital.

Table 3 : Annual fixed cost of Rice bran oil unit

Sr. No.	Particulars	Rs/year (lakhs)	Value (Rs/ton)
1	Depreciation on machinery	700.80 (81.93)	17071.90
2	Depreciation on building	9.93 (1.16)	241.81
3	Depreciation on furniture	2.42 (0.28)	58.94
4	Taxes and insurance	3.99 (0.47)	97.44
5	Permanent employee's salary	60.45 (7.07)	1472.59
6	Interest on fixed capital	77.76 (9.09)	1894.27
	Total	855.36 (100.00)	20836.95

As revealed from this table 3, the total average fixed cost for Rice bran oil unit was Rs. 855.36 lakhs. It is observed from table that depreciation on machinery accounted 81.93 per cent followed by interest on fixed capital accounted 9.09 per cent. The permanent employee's salary was accounted 7.07 per cent whereas depreciation on building accounted 1.16 per cent of the total fixed cost. The taxes

and insurance accounted 0.47 per cent and depreciation on furniture accounted 0.28 per cent of the total fixed cost.

Annual variable cost of Rice bran oil unit

The variable cost consists of expenditure on purchase on raw material, wages of casual labour, oil and lubricants, repair and maintenance of machinery, packaging cost etc.

Table 4 : Annual variable cost of Rice bran oil unit

Sr. No.	Particulars	Rs/year (lakhs)	Value (Rs/ton)
1	Cost of raw materials	145.00 (79.03)	3532.28
2	Casual labour charges	18.30 (9.97)	445.80
3	Repair and maintenance	5.50 (2.99)	133.98
4	Energy, oil charges	2.73 (1.49)	66.50
5	Postage, stationary and telephone charges	1.55 (0.85)	37.87
6	Interest on working capital	10.39 (5.67)	252.99
	Total	183.47 (100.00)	4469.43

As evident from this Table 4, that the average variable cost for Rice bran oil unit was Rs. 183.57 lakhs. The composition of variable cost revealed that the cost of raw materials were 79.03 per cent followed

by casual labour charges 9.97 per cent. The interest on working capital accounted 5.67 per cent. The repair & maintenance accounted 2.99 per cent. The oil & energy charges accounted 1.49 per cent.

Postage, stationary and telephone charges were accounted 0.85 per cent of the total variable cost.

The marketing cost consists of cost of packaging, transportation, loading & unloading charges, market cess and other charges in the marketing cost of Rice bran oil unit.

Annual Marketing cost of Rice bran oil unit

Table 5 : Annual Marketing cost of Rice bran oil unit

Sr. No.	Particulars	Rs/year (lakhs)	Value (Rs/ton)
1	Packing charges	4.10 (4.55)	100
2	Hamali charges (loading and unloading)	4.10 (4.55)	100
3	Market cess and other	20.53 (22.73)	500
4	Transportation charges	61.58 (68.18)	1500
	Total	90.31 (100.00)	2200

It is revealed from Table 5 that, the total marketing cost required for marketing of rice bran oil was Rs. 90.31 lakhs. It was observed from table that transportation charges was major item which were Rs. 68.18 per cent of the total marketing cost. Market cess and other

accounted 22.73 per cent. Packing charges and hamali charges were equal which was 4.55 per cent each of the total marketing cost.

Total cost incurred by rice bran oil unit

Total cost incurred by Rice bran oil unit was the sum of fixed cost, variable cost and marketing cost incurred by producer.

Table 6 : Total cost incurred by rice bran oil unit

Sr. No	Particulars	Rs/year (lakhs)	Value (Rs/ton)
1	Fixed cost	855.36 (75.68)	20836.95
2	Variable cost	183.47 (16.33)	4469.43
	Sub total (1&2)	1038.83	25306.38
3	Marketing cost	90.31 (7.99)	2200
	Total cost incurred by the unit	1129.14 (100.00)	27506.37

It is revealed from Table 6 that, the total cost incurred by producer was accounted Rs. 1129.14 lakhs. The maximum cost share was for fixed cost which accounts 75.68 per cent. The per cent share of

variable cost was 16.33 per cent followed by marketing cost which were 7.99 per cent of total cost incurred by the rice bran oil unit.

Economics of Processing of Rice bran oil

Table 7 : Economics of Processing of Rice bran oil

Sr. No.	Particulars	Rs/year (lakhs)	Value (Rs/ton)
1	Production in ton	4105	-
2	Value of final product (Rs)	2930.55	71389.86
3	Gross return (Rs)	2930.55	71389.86
4	Total cost incurred by rice bran oil unit (Rs)	1129.14	27506.37
5	Net returns (Rs)	1801.42	43883.49
6	Benefit cost ratio	2.60	

Table 7 shows the economics of processing of rice bran oil. It was revealed from table that the gross returns of Rice bran oil unit was Rs. 71389.86 per ton. The gross returns taken by considering average of total value received from March 2022 to April 2023. Thus, Gross returns per ton obtained from processing of Rice bran oil was Rs. 71389.86.

The Benefit cost ratio was a ratio of total returns received from Rice bran oil processing to its total cost. The Benefit cost ratio of Rice bran oil unit was worked out to 1:2.60 means processing of rice bran oil is profitable venture, hence hypothesis is accepted.

Break even point analysis

Break even point shows the minimum size of volume to recover total cost required for processing in a year. One of the objective of present study was to study the break even point for Rice bran oil unit. Results are presented in this section.

Total cost incurred by rice bran oil unit was Rs. 27506.37 per ton which was calculated by adding fixed cost, variable cost and marketing cost. The Net returns received was calculated by subtracting total cost incurred by producer from gross returns. The Net returns per ton of rice bran oil unit was Rs. 43883.49

Table 8 : Break even point analysis of Rice bran oil unit

Sr. No.	Particulars	Value
1	Actual quantity processed per year in ton	4105
2	Annual fixed cost (Rs) F	85535648.59
3	Selling price per ton (Rs) P	71389.866

4	Variable cost per ton (Rs) V	4469.42
5	Breakeven point (tons) physical term	1278.17 ton
	Margin of safety in physical terms	2826.83 ton
	% of margin of safety	31.14%
6	Breakeven point (Rs) in monetary term	91248323.29 Rs
	Margin of safety in monetary terms	201807076.7 Rs
	% of margin of safety	31.14%

It is revealed from Table 8 that the Break even point was observed 1278.17 tons of the rice bran oil unit which indicated that a rice bran oil unit should produce a minimum of 1278.17 tons of oil so as to not incurred any losses. In monetary terms, breakeven point analysed was Rs. 91248323.29.

The margin of safety in monetary term of rice bran oil unit was Rs. 201807076.7 and margin of safety in physical term was 2826.83 tons. The percentage of margin of safety was 31.14 per cent.

Conclusions

The break even point in physical quantity for rice bran oil unit was 1278.17 tons. The break even point in monetary value for rice bran oil was Rs. 91248323.29. The margin of safety in monetary term of rice bran oil unit was 201807076.7 and margin of safety in physical term was 2826.83. The percentage of margin of safety was 31.14 per cent.

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